

METHODS OF DEVELOPING BIOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE OF BIOLOGY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912226>

Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research, the methodology of the development of the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research, the effectiveness of the development of the knowledge of biology students about modern methods of biological research were studied. Also, Methods of developing biological knowledge of biology students were analyzed.

Key words: biology, technology, competence, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, form, method, tool, evaluation, creative thinking, reflexivity, creativity, pedagogical experiment.

INTRODUCTION. It is aimed at creating and forming concepts in the minds of students, developing their thinking ability. Therefore, the teacher tries to organize the lesson by means of mental operations such as analysis, synthesis, and generalization. Problem-based learning, didactic games, conference classes, which serve to increase students' activity in the lesson, are especially good for mastering the concepts thoroughly. The issue of developing concepts is aimed not only at the acquisition of knowledge by students, but also at the formation and development of practical skills and abilities. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the organization of independent work of students when studying the subject.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Studies on the application of electronic educational resources and virtual educational technologies in the teaching of biology subjects in the continuing education system to the methodology of forming the professional competence of future biology teachers L. Ravlovsh, I. Bilous, N.E. Rerry, S.A. Brenner, Y.N. Arbuzova, S.B. Bogomolova, N.P. Stepanova, M.M. Salimova, N.A. Karimova, Z.A. Mardanov, A.K. Rakhimov, J.O. Tolipova; of Bakhodirova researched in his works.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In order to organize educational work according to the requirements for the development of concepts, the teacher should prepare for the lesson as follows.

1. Determining what concepts students need to develop in the subject studied according to the program requirement;

2. To determine the degree to which the concepts required by the program were reflected in the lessons;
3. Dividing the concepts of the newly studied topic into groups;
4. Ways to connect newly learned concepts with concepts learned in previous lessons;
5. Choosing the form of teaching that positively affects the learning of concepts;
6. Determining effective methods of teaching groups of new concepts;
7. Selection of lesson equipment that serves to form and strengthen concepts;
8. Determining the activities of the teacher and students in the exercise of learning concepts;
9. Finding ways to influence student activity in learning concepts;
10. Study of concepts should also include defining the use of scientific and methodical popular literature that serves enrichment.

It is known that the educational process in schools is carried out as a result of the joint activities of teachers and students. The chosen working methods of teachers in teaching students are called teaching methods or methodologies.

In the literature, the method is also interpreted as an activity to achieve a certain goal, a practical or theoretical method of assimilation of reality. That is probably why N.M. Verzilin and V.M. Korsunskaya define "Teaching method as the activity of the teacher in explaining knowledge to students, and at the same time in acquiring this knowledge by students." Such a definition of the method shows the activities of the teacher-provider and the students who acquire knowledge in mastering the educational material.

Any method is considered to be an activity consisting of a system of conscious actions aimed at the realization of a certain goal that a person has set for himself. Therefore, at the root of the application of any method, people have some goals.

A person uses different ways and means to achieve his goal. In the process of work, he monitors the results of the work being performed and makes the necessary corrections to it. He corrects the mistakes made.

There are different opinions in the literature about biology teaching methods. For example, according to Ye.P. Brunovt, he gave information about oral, demonstrative and practical methods, including methods such as explanation and demonstration, partial research and research. The author

shows that there are different types of oral method, such as story, story-conversation, conversation, work on a book, and written work.

I.D. Zverev oral and practical biology teaching methods depending on the sources of updating knowledge; it shows the teacher's explanation of new teaching methods depending on the activity of the teacher and students.

Also, in the works of various authors about teaching methods, information is provided about the existence of various methods that depend on the didactic tasks of education and serve the independence and activity of students.

N.M. Verzilin and V.M. Korsunskaya write about the use of 3 different methods in biology education. In our opinion, the instructions of these authors about the use of oral, visual and practical methods in biology education are very simple and correct. Because when studying the educational material, students need to hear, listen, see it or manage the practical activities that are convenient for them. For this reason, we currently use the above-mentioned three methods in biology education. It is known that the oral demonstration and practical methods used in biology education require teachers and students to be involved in different activities in learning the lesson material.

It is one of the first methods used in teaching since ancient times. The reason why this method is called oral is that the students learn the educational material as a result of the teacher's story, lecture, and conversation. In other words, when this method is used, students understand ready-made knowledge through the teacher's spoken words. The oral method provides an opportunity to explain the educational material through the teacher's lively, vividly emotional words, using various visual aids. If we pay attention to the past hundreds of years in the history of mankind, we can witness that several generations of learned people have acquired knowledge through the same oral method. Oral method includes similar methods such as story, conversation, lecture, explanation.

The story is usually a method used when the topic of the lesson is devoted to the history of the discovery of various scientific researches, the life and work of scientists, and the experience of a phenomenon or events in nature. The story method is often used in biology education. The story is usually a method used when the topic of the lesson is devoted to the history of the discovery of various scientific researches, the life and work of scientists, and the experience of a phenomenon or events in nature. The story is a vivid visual description of the educational material in the above content given by the teacher.

There are several requirements for the story method, and the following can be pointed out: the story should be told through the teacher's bright and vivid words.

1. A teacher who uses the story method should have artistic skills, pay attention to different actions, high or low volume of the voice while explaining different parts of the lesson, and tell stories with excitement.

2. The story should be organized in the direction of the plot, such as setting the main issues of the lesson topic, ways of solving it, solving and drawing conclusions.

3. As mentioned above, since the story is often used in the lower classes, it is necessary to take into account the mental capabilities and attention skills of the students of this class. Psychologists have shown that 13-15-year-old students focus their attention on topics and events for 12-15 minutes, and then their attention shifts to other things. sending is not appropriate. When the story method is used, the teacher should pay attention to the comprehensibility and demonstration of his speech. Therefore, he should use various visual aids related to the content of the lesson during the story.

4. The story method requires the teacher to have a certain speech culture. His speech should be fluent, artistic, and he should not repeat certain words ("I mean", "Therefore").

5. While telling a story, the teacher should speak like a person who has seen the natural phenomenon he is describing, worked side by side with scientists, participated in the discovery of scientific discoveries. In conversation, the methods are used when the content of the lesson is somewhat familiar to the students, they have seen it in their daily life, and they are dedicated to the topics they know. The interview is aimed at learning the content of the lesson and is conducted on the basis of the answers given by the students to the questions prepared by the teacher. When using the conversation method, the teacher does not tell the content of the lesson, but asks the students questions arising from the subject of the lesson, and gets answers to these questions. When creating questions for the interview, the teacher studies the content of the lesson and its main concepts. Then, he works on the main concepts in the lesson, taking into account the knowledge reserves and life experiences of the students.

CONCLUSION. The role and importance of extracurricular activities in the formation of students' scientific worldview is incomparable. Observations conducted by students in nature during such activities, and the results of

practical work at the school's educational and experimental site also serve to obtain convincing evidence.

In conclusion, in order to educate students' scientific outlook, the teacher should not limit himself to teaching students the knowledge required by the program, but should always take into account the ways and means of educating students depending on the content of the lesson.

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